

ReceptioGate: Public legal clarification following a decision of the Swiss Federal Administrative Court (2026) concerning *The Book of Hours of Louis de Roucy*

By decision of the **Swiss Federal Administrative Court** dated **7 January 2026**, the proceedings concerning the volume *The Book of Hours of Louis de Roucy* have been **definitively closed**.

The volume, authored by **Carla Rossi** and dedicated to the study and digital reconstruction of a dismembered medieval manuscript, had been placed at the centre of an extensive **online polemical narrative**, initiated through materials and interventions disseminated by **Peter Kidd**, which later became known as *ReceptioGate*.

The Court **annulled the withdrawal**, by the **Swiss National Science Foundation**, of the research grant related to this book and held that **there are no grounds to qualify the work as plagiarised or to impose sanctions**. The allegations examined by the Court did not withstand judicial scrutiny.

The ruling definitively clarifies that accusations and reconstructions based on **online-circulated materials and claims** did not find **legal confirmation**. It reaffirms the necessity of clearly distinguishing between public online debate and **scholarly evaluation grounded in verifiable criteria and proper fact-finding**.

ISFiDa reiterates its commitment to the **protection of medieval manuscripts**, to **research based on documented and verifiable sources**, and to the responsible use of digital tools in scholarly communication and assessment.